

ESTABLISHING PSYCHOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT AND COUNSELING CENTER AT LSPU - SPCC: A DESCRIPTIVE FEASIBILITY STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to assess the possible establishment of psychological assessment and counseling center at Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City Campus. Specifically, it aimed to assess its feasibility, acceptability and potential sustainability. Opinion of community stakeholders were also gathered as one of the research's primary objectives, which is to provide basic mental health services to the community. This study used exploratory mix method of quantitative and qualitative research which utilized a researcher-made survey questionnaire with 150 working respondents from which 15 were subjected to unstructured in-depth interview. They were the ones who were residents of San Pablo City and other nearby municipalities namely: Victoria, Calauan, Alaminos, Nagcarlan, Rizal, and Liliw. Findings revealed that establishing a psychological assessment and counseling center at LSPU, San Pablo was feasible in terms of the number of psychometricians and other mental health professionals available. In addition, it was acceptable in terms of the qualification of test administrators and its location as it lies at the center of 3rd district of Laguna. Moreover, it was sustainable in terms of the number of clients it can possibly have. However further considerations were raised by the respondents such as the existing conditions of LSPU-SPCC and its potential capacity to establish the said centers such as the aspects of human resources, physical facilities, funding and community eagerness.

Keywords: Psychology, Counseling, Descriptive Survey. State University, Philippines